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SHAPING INDUSTRY FROM THE LEFT IN EUROPE

COUNTRY REPORT POLAND

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Introduction

Between 1989 and 2015, the Polish economy underwent many major changes. The essential, of course, was a systemic transition from socialism to capitalism. This transformation process lasted for many years and revealed its consequences at varied strengths over different periods. Another crucial factor in shaping the modern economic order in Poland was the accession to the European Union in 2004. The global economic crisis of 2008 was also significant in this respect. All the aforementioned, along with some specifically Polish circumstances, create a dynamic picture of the Polish economy in the last quarter of a century. The changes that took place in this period apply to virtually all areas of social and economic life: the structure of the economy, national income distribution, politics, the labour market, demography, the social security system, and finance. This report is an attempt to discuss the changes that have occurred in Poland in all these areas in the last 25 years. Its aim is to contribute to the discussion on progressive European industrial policy.

Unless otherwise indicated, data presented in this report comes from the public databases of such institutions as the European Commission (both Eurostat and AMECO), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the International Labour Organization (ILO) and the Central Statistical Office of Poland. Although, in the case of Poland the obvious historical turning point is 1990, many time series (especially in the area of national accounting) begin in 1995 due to the transition to ESA95 accounting standards undertaken at that time. Any, other than those in 1990 or 1995, initial observations (e.g. 1997, 2000 or 2004) are only due to limitations in the availability of the data. These limitations do not affect the quality of the analysis, since they do not prevent inter-temporal comparative studies, even if they slightly reduce its perspective.

Chapter 1: Gross Domestic Product and the structure of the economy

In 25 years of Poland's new capitalism, its economy has experienced periods of both strong economic growth and slowdown, or even decline in gross domestic product. The first years of the transformation were marked by a sudden collapse of the economy, which was reflected in GDP decline in 1990-1991 by a total of 18.6%. Since 1992, however, the Polish economy continues to grow, although the rate of growth varies significantly – from 1.2% in 2001 to 7.2% in 2007. The latter, indicating a very high GDP growth just before the global economic crisis, partially explains why in the subsequent years, unlike most developed economies, Poland has not experienced negative growth: the decline in GDP growth in the following years was to some extent absorbed by its very high initial level.

Chart 1.1. Gross domestic product (chain linked volume, percentage change over previous period).

Source: Eurostat, Central Statistical Office of Poland.

More about Polish economic growth in the past two decades can be learned from analysing the structure of the Polish GDP from the expenditure side. Eurostat data for the years 1995-2014 show, firstly, a very stable share of general government

expenditures in GDP, constantly falling within the range of 17.7-19.3%. Secondly, although by 2002 the share of private consumption in gross domestic product had steadily grown (from 58.3% in 1995 to 65.6% in 2002), before starting to undergo a systematic, and to this day ongoing, decline (to 59.4% in 2014), the percentage should be considered relatively stable, especially compared with investment and foreign trade.

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) as a percentage of GDP in the discussed period experienced two intervals of expansion: in the years 1995-1999 (from 17.4% to 24.3%) and in 2004-2008 (from 18.1% to 22.6%). There is therefore no coincidence in that these particular periods are the same as the periods of the highest GDP growth in Poland. Importantly, general government expenditure includes gross fixed capital formation as well. Between 2002 and 2012, government's investment's share in GDP varied in the range of 3.3%-5.7%, with a peak in 2009-2011 (5.2%-5.7% of GDP). Using the pretext of preparations for the organization of the UEFA Euro 2012 football championships, the Polish conservative-liberal government boosted the economy in a 'Keynesian' manner. According to the Eurostat data, Poland's 5.7% share of government's GFCF in GDP in 2011 was the highest public investment ratio in the European Union.

Chart 1.2. Structure of the Polish gross domestic product from the expenditure side (% of GDP).

Source: Eurostat.

The most significant, however, is the evolution of the share of Polish exports and imports in GDP. In the discussed period, this percentage more than doubled for both of these categories (from 23.0% to 46.7% for exports and from 20.7% to 45.2% for imports), which indicates a drastic increase in the importance of foreign trade in shaping Polish national income.

Chart 1.3. Adjusted wage share (% of GDP).

Source: AMECO.

Additional crucial information about the national income in Poland and its relationship with the structural changes taking place in the economy can be provided by an analysis of GDP from the income side, in particular by the data on wage share and profit share. According to the European Commission (AMECO), in 1992, among the countries now members of the European Union, only the Netherlands had a slightly higher adjusted wage share (compensation per employee as percentage of GDP at market prices per person employed) than Poland, with its rate of 64.2%. By 2014, however, the ratio for Poland was drastically reduced – especially in the years 2001-2005, when it fell by 9 percentage points – to reach record low 47.2% in 2014, the fifth worst result in the European Union (after Slovakia, Lithuania, Cyprus and Romania) with average of 56.3%. Data on non-adjusted wage share as well as on the profit share are consistent with the above. In 2012, Poland had the third lowest share of compensation of employees in GDP in the EU (after Greece and Romania), amounting to 36.1%, with the average for the EU28 of 49.5%, and the fourth highest share of gross operating surplus and gross mixed income in GDP (after Greece, Romania and Slovakia), amounting to 51.4%, while the average for the EU28 was only 38.4%.

Chart 1.4. Real compensation of workers, real unit labour costs and real productivity of labour (1995=100).

Source: AMECO, Eurostat.

Socio-economic causes for the development of the situation in Poland will be discussed later in this report. At this point, one should only pay attention to the interconnection between labour productivity growth, wage growth and the dynamics of labour costs, which seem to be directly related to the problem of increasing unfairness in the distribution of national income. In the years 1995-2013, real labour productivity per person employed experienced the fourth highest (after Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia) growth among the countries currently in the European Union. It increased by 97.6% (in 1995 prices), while the same ratio for the EU27 increased by only 20.4%. At the same time, however, real compensation per employee in Poland increased by a mere 62.0%, and real unit labour costs (the ratio of compensation per employee to nominal GDP per person employed) fell by 18.9% (by 29.3% from 1992), which was the second highest decrease of this ratio in the European Union (after Romania).

As far as private business profitability is concerned, it is worth mentioning one more indicator that emphasizes the argument presented above. AMECO data shows that the 1995-2014 period in Poland was a time of almost uninterrupted growth of net returns on net capital stock, in 2014 reaching twice the basic value (in 1995 prices). Meanwhile, for twenty eight countries in the European Union, this ratio, after an increase of 25.3% by 2007, since the 2008 economic crisis, in 2014 dropped to eventually only 8.2% higher than two decades before.

Chart 1.5. Net returns on net capital stock (1995=100).

Source: AMECO.

As a result of economic transition from socialism to capitalism, the structure of the

Polish economy has undergone a significant change. According to the Central Statistical Office of Poland, the five most important industries in Poland in 1995, in terms of their share in gross value added, were manufacturing (20.2%), trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (18.5%), agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing (7.9%), construction (7.7%), and public administration, defence and compulsory social security (6.7%). Since then, manufacturing lost some of its significance (decrease to 17.7% in 2013), already losing first place in this ranking in 2000 to trade (with 19.3% share in the gross value added in 2013). In time, agriculture and public administration also fell out of the top five, giving way to industries like transportation and storage (6.8% of the gross value added in 2013), and real estate activities (5.9%).

Chart 1.6. Five industries with highest share in total gross value added (%).

Source: Central Statistical Office of Poland.

This means that in capitalist Poland not just the process, ongoing throughout socialism, of reducing the importance of the agricultural sector while strengthening industry, has been somewhat completed, but above all, there has begun a new process that leaves industry behind the services sector. This conclusion is confirmed by data on the share of employment in various sectors in total employment in Poland. While back in 2000, according to the International Labour Organization, employment in agriculture and related amounted to 18.7% of total employment in Polish economy. In 2013 it was only 12.0%. In the same period, the most significant

increase was in combined employment in trade, transportation, business and administrative services, accommodation and food – from 28.0% in 2000 to 33.8% in 2013. Interestingly, according to the same data, the share of employment in public administration (in the broad sense) in total employment also increased – from 22.3% to 23.4%.

Chart 1.7. Total receipts from taxes and social contributions (including imputed social contributions) after deduction of amounts assessed but unlikely to be collected (% of GDP).

Source: Eurostat.

This, however, does not mean there is or has been a strong commitment by the Polish state in the economy. The data presented earlier on the scale of the general government's gross fixed capital formation may appear misleading in that regard. Polish governments, especially in the first two decades of systemic transformation, were gradually limiting their involvement in the economy. It can be well illustrated by tax data, specifically on the evolution of total receipts from taxes and social contributions (including imputed social contributions) after deduction of amounts assessed but unlikely to be collected as a percentage of GDP. While in the years 1995-2012 this ratio for the twenty-seven European Union countries fluctuated steadily around 40% (from 41.8% in 1999 to 39.6% in 2009-2010), in Poland between 1995 and 2004, it decreased from 37.1% to 31.5%, and in 2012, after a temporary increase, was still only 32.5%.

Chart 1.8. Exports to (imports from) the European Union as a percentage of

total exports (imports) of goods and services.

Source: Eurostat.

As mentioned before, in the last two decades the importance of foreign trade in shaping Polish national income has increased dramatically. One should therefore look at a few of its most important structural characteristics. Firstly, it has to be noted that, despite some fluctuation in this regard, the European Union countries have a predominant share in both Polish exports and imports. In the years 1995-2013, exports to the European Union as a percentage of total exports of goods and services ranged (from the lowest to the highest) 72.6% in 1997 81.0% two years later, while imports from the European Union as a percentage of total imports of goods and services varied from 68.5% in 2000 to 76.7% in 2004. Interestingly, from the years 2003-2004 on, and therefore since the Polish accession to the European Union, these percentages are slowly but steadily declining. The reason for such a situation can be both the growing importance of Poland's new trading partners outside the EU (e.g. China), as well as the fact that since the establishment of the euro area, some of Poland's major trading partners in the European Union have begun to focus their trade efforts within the Eurozone.

Chart 1.9. Three most important Poland's trade partners (% of total export/import).

Source: Central Statistical Office of Poland.

Note: The colours indicate, respectively: navy blue – Germany, red – USSR/Russia, blue – Italy, orange – China, purple – France, green – the Netherlands, yellow – Great Britain, dark green – Czech Republic.

In regards to the most important Poland's trade partners, the composition of this group seems to be quite consistent over the years from 1990-2013. Throughout this period, the most important Polish trade partner, both in terms of exports and imports, was Germany. As far as exports are concerned, from 1990 to 1995, the Polish western neighbour made a significant leap in its share (from 25.1% to 38.3%), largely as a result of the attempts of Polish exporters to compensate for the loss of market in the former Soviet Union (down from second place occupied by the USSR in 1990, with share of 15.3% of Polish exports, to third place with only 5.6% in 1995, as Russia.). Since then, Germany's share in Polish exports decreased steadily, and in 2013 returned to the 1990 ratio, At the same time, since 1995 there has been no country from outside the European Union in the top three Polish export partners, and the group is fairly constant (France, Italy, United Kingdom, joined by the Czech Republic only in 2013).

In the years 1990-1995, Poland also recorded a sharp increase in imports from Germany (from 20.1% to 26.6%), which – just like exports to this country – has since been steadily decreasing. Interestingly, unlike in the case of exports, Russia has not dropped out of the top three countries with the largest share in Polish imports, and with the exception of 1995 it persists second in this ranking. Undoubtedly, the import of fossil fuels is of great importance in this respect. Until 2005, the third most

important Polish trade partner with respect to imports was Italy, which, however, since 2010 has been replaced in this role by China (obvious reasons including a growing China's position in the global economy need no further explanation).

The sectoral structure of Poland's foreign trade is rather homogeneous and remains stable. About 95% of Polish exports (96.0% in 2006, 94.6% in 2013) is manufactured production, which also account for some 85% of Polish imports (86.8% in 2006, 83.2% in 2013). The second largest share in Polish imports are products of mining and quarrying (8.0% in 2006, 10.1% in 2013). More important than the very sectoral structure of foreign trade, especially of exports, seems to be the latter's participation in global value chains. According to OECD data, in 2009, backward participation (the percentage of foreign input/value added included in country's exports) was 28% in the case of Polish exports, while the forward participation (the domestic sector/value added of the country contained in the exports of other countries) was 20%. High forward participation characterized the service industries (especially wholesale and retail, as well as business services), while manufacturing (in particular chemicals and transport equipment, to a lesser extent machinery and electrical equipment) had the highest backward participation degree.

Another important macroeconomic category in the area of balance of payments is Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). According to the World Bank data, since 1990 its value measured as a share of GDP grew steadily until 2000, when it reached 5.4%. After three years of decline, since 2004 it has returned to the path of expansion and in 2006 achieved a record high 6.3%. Since then, the percentage has been falling steadily, in 2013 showing even a negative value. There are various explanations of this complex phenomenon, one of which is a very liberal policy of the Polish governments, also towards FDI. For instance, the authors of an interesting study on this topic have noted: "Unlike many developing countries, which strongly encouraged export orientation of foreign-controlled companies in order to lower the negative consequences of FDI on their balance of payments, Poland has followed quite liberal policies in that respect after 1990. Despite that, the strategies of multinational companies entering the Polish market were based on a strong involvement of their subsidiaries in export operations. This is quite surprising in view of a sizeable domestic market with 38 million inhabitants which normally facilitates implementation of market-seeking strategies. (Jerzy Cieřlik, Eugeniusz Kaćiak," Foreign Subsidiaries in Emerging Markets and Export Performance: The Case of Poland," *Master of Business Administration* 4/2011 (114), p. 21)

Chart 1.10. Net inflows of Foreign Direct Investment (% of GDP).

Source: The World Bank.

Chapter 2: Political structure

In Poland, a unitary state, much of the power of a state rests in the hands of the central government. The prerogatives of the local government include management of public schools, cultural institutions, local health units and local road systems; maintenance of public facilities; administrative service of citizens; development of physical culture and tourism; land management; social assistance and combating unemployment. Although this may seem quite a lot, one should bear in mind that the vast majority of the resources available to Polish local government comes from a subsidy from the state budget, since local taxes are very limited in scale. Besides, most of the aforementioned tasks are rather administrative and local in nature. Therefore, without major oversimplification, it can be assumed that economic and development policies in Poland are being conducted by the central government.

The cornerstone of a political order in Poland is the total and undeniable consensus of all parliamentary political forces in terms of economic policy, a vision of how the economy functions and interests in which social groups should be represented by the political establishment. With one exception of a moderate social democratic period in the Labour Union party, attributable to its opposition years (1993-1997), in Polish parliament for the last quarter of century there has been no political force, which in terms of the economic program could be defined as even partially leftist/progressive. In the years 1989-1993, 1997-2001, and continuously since 2005, Poland has been governed by conservative-liberal (right wing) parties or coalitions, while in 1993-1997 and 2001-2005 – by the post-communists, each time in a coalition with a rural conservative party. The economic policy of the post-communist party, however – except for certain aspects of its policies in the years 1993-1997 – did not substantially differ from the right-wing governments' policies. Throughout the entire period in question, Polish politics is thus very consistent in its neoliberalism.

For example, the corporate tax rate has been consistently reduced by successive governments, regardless of their political labels. In 1992 the rate was 40%, in 2000 – 30%, and since 2004 it has been 19% (currently 7th lowest in the European Union). Interestingly, the biggest single reduction in the corporate tax rate (from 27% to 19%) was introduced by the post-communist party (Democratic Left Alliance), consistently defining itself as 'leftist' and at the same time, even today, proclaiming this reduction the greatest economic achievement in the party's history. The same applies to fiscal policy. Total general government expenditure, that in 1996 still accounted for 51.0% of Polish GDP (compared to the average for the EU27 of

49.7%), until 2000 was reduced to 41.1% (3.6 percentage points below the EU average), and since then hovers around 42%-44%, in 2013 amounting to 41.9% (with an EU28 average of 49.1%). As far as the total general government revenue is concerned, in a very short period of time (1996-2000) it decreased dramatically from 46.1% to 38.1% of GDP. Since then, only in two years did this ratio exceed 40% (reaching 40.2-40.3% in 2006-2007). In 2013, the rate was 37.5%, with an average of 45.7% for the EU28.

Particularly important in Polish economic policy over the last two and a half decades was privatization. As it was always especially crucial for conservative-liberal governments, it should not surprise that in 1997-2000, Poland experienced a kind of 'privatization spree'. According to the OECD data, revenues from privatization in this period ranged from 2.2 billion USD in 1997 to record 6.2 billion USD in 2000. The second large (although much smaller than the previous one) wave of privatization was in 2004-2005 and was more of a response to prolonged social crisis. Moreover, the large value of privatization in this period corresponded to higher values of individual contracts (sale of state monopolies, e.g. telecom) and not to the mass character of privatization itself.

A slavish devotion by Polish political class to the neoliberal, free-market ideology is the main reason for its distorted idea of economic development and its policy. Since Poland's entrance on the path of capitalism, all the ruling forces had two main 'development' objectives: the aforementioned mass privatization and membership in the EU. After almost complete privatization and the accession to the European Union in 2004, the main and, as it seems, probably the sole 'development' purpose of Polish political elite is to extract as much funds as possible from the EU cohesion policy pool. It is worth noting that – paradoxically – the Polish politicians' new objectives appear to be still better for the economy than the previous obsession with privatization and scale of fiscalisation. In the 2004-2013 period, cohesion policy funds accounted for on average 2.3% of Polish GDP, which was undoubtedly one of the factors that made the 2008 global crisis hit the Polish economy with less force.

Commitment of practically all Polish mainstream politicians to pro-business actions is so blatant and, on the other hand, the voice of business lobby so openly and exclusively represented in the media (both corporate and public) that any regulations in terms of interconnection of politics and business can only be a facade. On the one hand, there is not a single daily newspaper in Poland that would identify itself as a left-wing, and only one such weekly, which, however, represents an option similar to

the post-communist Democratic Left Alliance neoliberal party. On the other hand, views that in any western democracy would probably be immediately recognized as inadmissible – are being perceived in the mainstream as a completely natural and normal.

Indeed, the 2005 bill on lobbying activities in the law-making process is a residual regulation, which applies only to the laws and regulations of ministers, prime minister and government. A lobbyist is only required to register, but does not have to submit reports (the reporting obligation rests on the state). At the same time, lobbyists were given extensive powers, like the ability to perform their activities in offices servicing public authority. The bill is therefore widely criticized as not fulfilling its role.

Chapter 3: Debt structure

The 1997 Constitution of Poland stipulates that the ratio of (gross) public debt to GDP must not exceed 60%, while the Public Finance Act, detailing the provisions of the Constitution, has introduced two additional statutory safety thresholds, at 50% and 55%. In the case of exceeding of the latter, the government may be even required to balance the budget in the next fiscal year. In July 2013, the Polish government suspended the validity of the first of these safety thresholds, the others, however, still apply. Therefore, in the discussed period, Polish gross public debt to GDP ratio did not exceed 60%, and only once, in 2013, exceeded 55%.

The latter situation, and the measures taken by the government in the years 2013-14 to overcome it, requires some additional comment. As part of the 1999 reform of the Polish pension system, the PAYG solution has been replaced with a mixed system combining PAYG and capital parts. Under these new circumstances, Private Open Pension Funds (OPFs), the capital component of the system, were receiving part of pension contributions, half of which they constantly earmarked for the purchase of government bonds and other Treasury securities. The Public Social Insurance Institution, required to transfer part of the received pension contributions to the capital component of the system, therefore lacked the funds for current PAYG pension payments. This deficit was being covered by the government, thereby increasing its budget deficit, and thus the debt. In the end, the government had to incur debt to be able to transfer funds to the OPFs, for which the OPFs, after deduction of commission fees, were buying debt incurred by the State in the form of Treasury bonds. The only practical effects of this circulation of funds were higher budget deficits, higher debts and a higher level of the latter's profitability. Therefore, following the bill initiated by the government and passed by the Polish parliament in 2013, at the beginning of 2014 bonds held by the OPFs were transferred to Social Security, and then cancelled, so that the gross debt-to-GDP ratio declined significantly in 2014 (to 49.4% compared to 57.1% in 2013, according to IMF forecasts).

Chart 3.1. Consolidated general government gross and net debt-to-GDP ratios (%).

Source: International Monetary Fund.

In the discussed period, the gross debt to GDP ratio, as calculated by the IMF, varied from 36.8% in 2000, to the aforementioned 57.1% in 2013. Responsibility for its growth in the years 2000-2013 bears primarily an increase in central government debt (from 35.1% to 53.2%) which represents the vast majority of general government debt in Poland (2013 local government debt accounted for 7.2% of the nominal value of general government debt). It is, however, worth noting that the local government debt-to-GDP ratio, although small in size in the period 2000-2013, was characterized by dynamics much higher than the central government debt – it increased from 1.1% in 2000 to 4.2% in 2013.

The above image of low public debt in Poland, limited primarily by the constitutional provisions on the safety threshold, can be complemented by introducing a measure of net debt. According to the IMF's World Economic Outlook (October 2014 edition): "Net debt is calculated as gross debt minus financial assets corresponding to debt instruments. These financial assets are: monetary gold and SDRs, currency and deposits, debt securities, loans, insurance, pension, and standardized guarantee schemes, and other accounts receivable." This is consistent with an intuition that considering public debt burden one should refer not only to liabilities, but also to the corresponding assets. In the years 1995-2013, this ratio for Polish economy increased from -3.4% to 30.6%. The only tendency in the undisclosed future that may appear worrisome in this respect is that in recent years the growth of net debt-

to-GDP ratio has been much more dynamic compared to the corresponding ratio for the gross debt. While this first measure increased between 2008 and 2013 by over 208%, the latter only by approximately 21%. This, however, does not change the overall assessment of Poland's debt situation, essentially contingent upon formal issues and recent government policies.

As far as the maturity structure of Polish gross public debt is concerned, it is by far dominated by the short and medium-term instruments. In 2013, bonds with a maturity of 5 to 10 years accounted for 32.1% of Polish gross debt, with maturity of 10 to 15 years represented 28.2% of it, and instruments in the range of 1-5 years of maturity accounted for 27.5% of Polish general government indebtedness. At the same time, long-term bonds with maturity of more than 15 years accounted for only 12% of the Polish debt.

Chart 3.2. Maturity structure of gross public debt in 2013 (% of total).

Source: Eurostat.

Buyers' preference for rather short- and medium-term government bonds is easier to understand in the context of the purchasing structure of the debt. In 2013, a third (33.6%) of Polish government bonds were in the hands of financial corporations, another third (32.6%) in the hands of non-financial corporations, and almost all the rest (32.7%) were held by institutions representing the rest of the world. Thus, only 1.1% of Polish government debt was in the hands of households. Modern corporations, especially financial ones, are focused on rather short- and medium-term profit. Consequently, in the primary market they do not submit a high demand for long-term instruments, especially when the country is still perceived as not quite

stable due to being an "emerging market" or a "young democracy". This rule of thumb concerns even the aforementioned OPFs and therefore affects the maturity structure of the Polish sovereign debt.

No less important than public debt is the private, especially household indebtedness. Its analysis, however, should begin with an important macroeconomic remark: over the last twenty years in Poland, a serious gap between consumption and the income of the population has arisen. As it was already stated before in this report, while the share of household consumption in GDP remains quite constant and relatively high (since 1996 it has not fall below 60%), the adjusted wage share fell sharply (from 64.2% in 1992 to 47.3% in 2014). Moreover, in 2013 the percent of Polish households with a heavy financial burden due to housing costs reached 64.8% (from 37.3% just four years earlier), the third highest in the European Union (after Cyprus and Croatia), and far above the EU average of 38.0%. The first consequence of all the above was the sharp drop in gross household savings rate (from 16.9% in 1995 to 4.8% in 2012), but along with a strong decline of interest rates in Poland in the same period (as indicated by Eurostat data, 3-month money market interest rates fell from 27.6% in 1995 to 2.6% in 2014), those circumstances must have led to an increase in household debt.

Chart 3.3. Data on household debt and related.

Source: Eurostat.

Indeed, in the years 1995-2012, the gross debt-to-income ratio of Polish households increased from 3.1% to 53.9%. Particularly worrisome about this data, is not so much the level, as it is the dynamics of the phenomenon. For instance, although the level of the index in question for the 18 euro area countries (combined) was 98.3% in 2012, since 1995 it has increased by only 35%, while in Poland by as much as 520%.

Even though this problem affects most of the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, it seems that in Poland, more than in other economies, household indebtedness is so heavily based on a drastic and constantly deepening gap between the levels of household consumption and wage income combined with an extensive financial burden on households due to housing costs.

Chart 3.4. Corporation's debt, gross investment rate and gross profit share (%).

Source: Eurostat.

On the other hand, companies, especially non-financial ones, do not raise concerns with regard to debt. In the years 2003-2013, the non-financial corporations debt-to-GDP ratio increased only by a little more than 5 percentage points. This stability, indicating no rapidly growing need for external financing, becomes easier to understand considering that in the years 2000-2012, the gross investment rate of non-financial corporations fell from 38.2% to 21.1%, while the share of their gross profit increased from 36.7% to 49.1%. It therefore indicates that non-financial business economy's savings tend to grow, reducing its need to seek external sources of financing.

By the end of the last decade of the twentieth century, Poland struggled with the effects of hyperinflation from 1990 (in which year the average consumer price level, according to the IMF, increased compared to the previous year by almost 586%), an effect of the rapid transition from socialism to capitalism. This ratio was kept down to 5.5% in 2001 and since then the annual increase in Consumer Price Index (CPI) in Poland did not exceed 5%, and only in two years it exceeded 4% (reaching 4.2% in 2008 and 4.3% in 2011). The price increase is, of course, affected by a lot of factors,

but the trend is generally that inflation in Poland is low and declining. The latter mainly reflects tendencies in the Polish labour market (relatively low dynamics of nominal wage growth resulting from high unemployment, precarization of labour relations, etc.), especially since the beginning of the twenty-first century.

Chart 3.5. The dynamics of average consumer prices (year-over-year % change).

Source: International Monetary Fund.

The only problematic aspect of Polish inflation may be the 'social injustice' of price increase, that is its higher dynamics in the groups of goods and services essential to the majority of the population than, for example, in the case of luxury products. In Poland, this problem applies in particular to prices of housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels. According to Eurostat data, although the Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP) in the years 1995-2014 increased (at 1995 prices) by 118.1 points, in the above-mentioned group of goods and services, it grew by as much as 222 points.

Chapter 4: Population

According to official figures, the population of Poland in the last quarter of century remains fairly stable, fluctuating in the range of 38.0-38.5 million people. Apart from the reliability of these data in connection with migratory flows (see below), one should pay particular attention to the fact that the structure of Polish population is undergoing some changes. Firstly, as far as the age structure is concerned, according to Eurostat data, in the years 1990-2013 the percentage of the population of Poland aged 0-19 years decreased from 32.6% to 20.8%. The percentage of people aged 20-39 years has not fundamentally changed in this period (minimal increase from 30.8% to 31.1%), but the percentage of those aged 40-59 increased from 21.8% to 27.2%, while for those aged 60-79 increased from 12.8% to 17.1%. Finally, the percentage of people aged 80 years and more increased in the same period from 2.0% to 3.7%. It is thus evident that there has been a 'shift' in the share of the population from those under 19 to a group of people over 40, and therefore the problem of an aging population occurs. To complete the above image, the birth rate in Poland in the years 1993-2013 remains close to 0 (ranges from -0.1 to + 0.1%).

These demographic trends are slowly becoming reflected in the situation on the labour market. Employment rates for people aged 55-64, which in 1997, according to Eurostat, was 33.9%, after a temporary decrease in the period of severe socio-economic crisis of 2000-2004, is steadily rising since 2005, to achieve a record level of 40.6% in 2013. At the same time (1997-2013), the employment rate of people aged 15-24, although fluctuating, shows a slow downward trend – from 28.9% in 1997 to 24.2% in 2013. As far as the share of female employment in total employment is concerned, in the years 1997-2013 it remained fairly stable, fluctuating in the range of 44.2-45.4%.

It is also worth noting that – with a relatively constant official population – the number of households consisting of one adult is increasing (from 2.8 million in 2005 to 3.4 million in 2013), and responsible for this growth are virtually entirely households consisting of one adult without children (up from 2.3 to 2.9 million). This process, however, was not strong enough to affect the average household size, which in the years 2005-2013 remained at the same level – 2.8. Interestingly, most of these households are owners of the dwellings they reside in – according to Eurostat, in 2013, it was as much as 83.8%, with an EU average of 70%. It is worth noting that all EU member states from Central and Eastern Europe have this rate very high (with

the exception of Slovenia, where it amounted to 76.6%, in all of CEE countries it was greater than 80%, and in some, such as Lithuania, Romania and Slovakia, even more than 90%), due to their heritage of socialism. Providing only this percentage would, however, falsify the situation of Polish households as far as housing issues are concerned, since, as it was mentioned earlier, most of them are faced with heavy financial burdens due to housing costs (the third highest percentage of such households in the EU).

The level of labour union density in Poland has undergone a dramatic decline from 1990, and this process still proceeds. While in 1990, according to OECD data, 36.7% of wage and salary earners belonged to labour unions (with the average for the OECD of 26.3%), in 2012 it was only 12.5%, the 6th worst result in this group of countries (after Turkey, Estonia, France, Hungary and the USA), with the OECD average of 17.1%. There are several reasons for this course of events. Firstly, with the reintroduction of unemployment in Poland, people being dismissed from their jobs and/or becoming a long-term unemployed, or 'escaping' from unemployment by becoming pensioners, were somehow automatically losing contact with the labour union movement. Secondly, the two main trade unions in Poland were and still remain extremely politicized. For example, 'Solidarity' is historically associated with conservative-liberal parties, the alliance that resulted not only in the union's support for the dismantling of social and workers' rights systems in the early 1990s, but also in support for the 1997-2001 government's extreme neoliberal reforms. This situation strongly undermined public confidence in labour unions. Thirdly, for the last quarter of a century in Poland the unions have been a subject of constant media bashing, and to the general public they are presented almost exclusively in a negative manner, including persistent accusations of causing high unemployment by their very existence. Finally, Polish law allows organizing a union only by persons employed under an employment contract. Therefore, drastic precarization of labour relations in Poland since 2000 has significantly reduced the scope of this institution in society.

Chart 4.1. Estimated temporary emigration (in thousands).

Source: Central Statistical Office of Poland

After Poland's accession to the European Union and the opening of job markets for Poles by most of the existing member states, there has been a massive emigration of Polish labour force that in many ways shaped the present socio-economic order in Poland. While estimates by the Central Statistical Office mentioned 0.8 million Polish temporary residence emigrants in 2002, and 1.0 million in 2004, only two years later there were twice as many, and the following year emigration reached its peak of 2.3 million, or – in other words – 1.5 million more than just five years earlier (data for 2007-2013 refer to people who are temporarily abroad for more than three months, while for 2006 it includes persons staying temporarily abroad over 2 months). Since then, although it fluctuates, the number of Polish emigrants does not fall below 2 million. In 2013, it was 2.2 million, of which 1.8 million are in the EU (1.2 million in Germany and Great Britain combined). It is worth noting that these figures include people who – while keeping their formal permanent residence in Poland – reside outside the country. It often happens that they are staying abroad many years, but due to the fact that they formally did not give up their permanent residence in Poland, it still has to be assumed that their emigration is not definitive. As shown by the survey carried out by the Central Statistical Office, the main reason for going abroad is the desire to work there, but with time the percentage of people – members of the families of Polish immigrants (their dependents, e.g. spouse, children) also increases. It is estimated that more than 75% of the temporary Polish emigrants are staying abroad for at least 12 months.

The most immediate effect of emigration on the economy of the home country is, of course, workers' remittances. Due to the scale of Polish emigration, the net value of transfers increased between 2000 and 2007 more than five times, from 1.3 to 6.7 billion EUR. Although it has declined since then, in 2013 it was still almost 4 billion EUR. The importance of purchasing power coming from these funds is best demonstrated by their share in GDP. In 2000 it was 0.72% of Poland's gross domestic product, whereas in record 2007 went up to 2.14% (which was almost as much as the annual average of the EU's cohesion funds transferred to the Polish economy, since 2004 amounting to 2.3% of GDP). In 2013, it was still 1.01% of GDP.

Chart 4.2. Net workers' remittances (in mln EUR).

Source: Eurostat.

Data on the immigration to Poland is rudimentary and incomplete, in particular because of the difficulty in estimating the short-term labour migration and the problem of illegal immigration. However, both the available data and the overall assessment of the situation can indicate some trends in this regard. Firstly, Poland has not been a major destination country for immigrants. The Foreigners Office data shows that at the end of 2013, there were 121,000 immigrants in Poland – 0.31% of the population. Even if we add to the above the estimates of short-term labour immigration (260,000 in 2011), their total share in the Polish population still does not exceed 1%. However, together with some stabilization of the situation in Poland compared to the worst years of 2000-2005, and in connection with a wave of emigration from Poland, one can expect that in time it will become a more and more attractive place for immigrants, especially those seeking jobs. In particular, it might be the case with the citizens of Poland's eastern neighbours, especially Ukraine (Ukrainians are already the largest immigrant group in Poland).

Chart 4.3. Gini Index (income distribution).

Source: The World Bank.

Finally, regarding income inequality, the last twenty-five years in Poland can be divided into two periods: its rapid growth until 2004, and the slow decline since then. The socialist economy was characterized by relatively moderate levels of inequality. In 1989, the Gini index was 26.9. Capitalism, on the other hand, is inherently unjust (in terms of distribution of national income, the existence of unemployment, etc.), so once reintroduced, Poland's income inequality began to rise. In 1996, it already amounted to 32.7, and in 2004 reached a record high 35.4 (an increase of 31.6% over 15 years). Since then, however, the Gini income index, according to the World Bank, is steadily, albeit very slowly, declining. In 2011 it amounted to 32.8, and therefore it was 2.6 points lower than at its peak, but still 5.9 points higher than at the end of socialism. It should also be noted that there are some serious problems with the Gini index, the measuring of which is based on – in this case quite unreliably – survey methods. As the richest show a strong aversion to disclosing their income, the Gini index tends to be permanently underestimated. Indeed, there are studies based on fragmentary tax data that suggest Poland's Gini index can be up to dozen percentage points higher than the official measure.

Changes in the level of inequality in Poland in recent years are, however, to some extent confirmed by other indicators. The quintile measure is the ratio of equalized income share of the fifth to the first quintile. In 2005 Poland's was 6.62, the fourth highest in the European Union. By 2013, however, it dropped to the level of 4.86, below the EU28 average of 4.89. The same applies to a decile measure – in 2005 the third highest in the EU (12.23), and falling to 7.74 in 2013, below the EU average of

7.93. The slow decline in inequality in the last decade undoubtedly results from the already mentioned general improvement of the socio-economic situation in the recent years, in particular in comparison to the worst period of the first half of the twenty-first century's first decade.

One of the most dramatic effects of social inequality is always poverty and exclusion. The percentage of population at risk of social exclusion decreased significantly in the years 2005-2013, from 45.3% to 25.8%. This percentage for women does not show significant differences compared to the general population. The same applies to persons aged 18-64 years. Instead, it is consistently higher for those under 18 years of age (48.0% in 2005, 29.8% in 2013), which is certainly a cause for concern. On the other hand, the rate for people aged 65 years and more at risk of social exclusion is permanently significantly lower than the percentage for the total population (39.3% in 2005, 19.7% in 2013). This is undoubtedly related to the existence of a universal public pension system (described above), regardless of the changes it is subjected to, as well as of social benefits for the elderly (described below).

The severe material deprivation rate experienced in the same period a similar decline as percentage of population at risk of social exclusion – from 33.8% in 2005 to 11.9% in 2013. In this case, none of the age groups or women had values of this indicator significantly different compared to the total population. In addition, despite a slight decrease from 2005 to 2013 (from 13.8% to 10.8%), the in-work, at-risk-of-poverty rate of employed people aged from 18 to 64 remains relatively stable, although consistently above the EU average (8.9% in 2013). It is worth noting that in the case of both aforementioned variables the declines followed from very high levels, which arose in the first fifteen years of capitalism in Poland, especially in the years 2000-2005. These decreases should be associated with general socio-economic changes at this time, such as the mass labour emigration of Poles to Western Europe as well as the accompanying decline in unemployment and the inflow of workers' remittances (and, on the other hand, of the EU's cohesion policy funds).

Chapter 5: Labour Market

The socialist economy was characterized by full employment guaranteed by the state. The employment was, at the same time, almost exclusively in the public sector, which in socialism is responsible for the vast majority of economic activity. Launched in 1989, the transition towards capitalism brought a change in this respect, reintroducing unemployment in Poland, after more than four decades of full employment. The suddenness of the changes, especially the collapse of some of the state-owned industries, and the lack of preparation for the abrupt competition from private foreign companies and very speedy privatization, resulted in unemployment hitting Polish society with ferocity and strength. Starting from full employment in 1989, after only two years of capitalism (by the end of 1991) the registered unemployment rate in Poland amounted to 12.2%, and reached 16.4% another two years later. It is worth noting that, in macroeconomic terms, the surge in unemployment rate from 0 to 12.2% is attributable to a sharp decline in GDP, a total of 18.6% in the years 1990-1991.

When the post-communists came to power in 1993, they not only inhibited the increase in unemployment, reducing the scale of privatization and cuts in public spending, but also managed to achieve its significant decline. At the end of the term in 1997, the registered unemployment rate was 10.3%. Very important was certainly the glowing economic situation of this period – in the years 1994-1997, the average annual GDP growth rate was 6.4%. The victory in the elections of the same year of the post-Solidarity conservative-liberal coalition, however, meant returning the economy to the fully neoliberal tracks and, therefore, a renewed rise in unemployment – to 17.5% in 2001.

The 2001-2005 period was by far the worst for the Polish labour market. A combination of factors both domestic (privatization again intensified since 1997, further neoliberal reforms, budget cuts policy) and foreign (series of crises in the world, from East Asia and Russia, to the bursting of the dotcom bubble in the United States) contributed to a serious slowdown in the economy. It made the new post-communist government, which had been elected in the 2001, not only fail to reduce unemployment inherited from the previous government, but – on the contrary – resulted in the latter reaching record proportions. In 2002-2003, the registered unemployment rate was as high as 20%, and for five years (2001-2005) its annual average was 18.9%.

The decline in unemployment in subsequent years was influenced primarily by two factors: a strong economic recovery (in 2004-2007 the average annual GDP growth was 5.5%), and Polish accession to the European Union, which quickly resulted in a huge labour emigration from Poland. Indeed, the latter is a factor that permanently shaped the situation on the Polish labour market, preventing registered unemployment rate from exceeding 14% since 2007, although as a consequence of the global economic crisis of 2008, it increased to 13.4% in 2012-2013 from a record low (since 1991) of 9.5% in 2008. At this point, the already abovementioned relationship of the unemployment rate and economic growth in Poland should be addressed. The data suggests that the unemployment rate starts to decrease only when economic growth exceeds 5% per annum. This would mean, especially in the face of the increasing stagnation tendencies in developed capitalist economies, that Poland is experiencing long periods of so-called jobless growth.

Yet another question requires attention in this area of interest. The Labour Force Survey unemployment rate (measured since 1997) up to 2006 did not differ substantially from the estimations of the Central Statistical Office of Poland on the registered unemployment rate (the deviation never exceed 1 percentage point). From 2007 on, the indications based on the Labour Force Survey are from 1.6 percentage points in 2007, to as much as 4 percentage points in 2009, lower than the official unemployment rate. It seems that these differences reveal the growing problem for the past 10-15 years of the Polish labour market, namely its precarization. The most likely explanation is in this case that many casual employees, or those employed either temporarily or in the shadow economy – that is, generally, in very precarious conditions that do not guarantee access to public services, especially health care – register themselves as unemployed in order to be able to use basic public goods and services. It thereby overstates the rate of registered unemployment, and in practice means transferring the cost of private business onto society.

Chart 5.1. Rates of unemployment (registered and Labour Force Survey, %).

Source: Eurostat, Central Statistical Office of Poland.

Another important structural feature of Polish unemployment is its higher rate among women. From 1997 to 2014, according to the Labour Force Survey data, the unemployment rate among women in Poland was from 0.3 percentage points in 2010 to 2.1 percentage points in 1997 and 2000 higher than the total unemployment rate. Not in a single year of that period, however, was this rate lower. This indicates that the unemployment rate in Poland is still one of the areas of the labour market in which women are discriminated against. As far as the unemployment rate among young people (under 25) is concerned, despite the fact that it was almost half the size of the record level of 2002-2003, when it oscillated at 42% (the highest percentage among the 28 EU member countries), in 2014 it still was the 8th largest ratio in the EU, exceeding the average (23.9% against 22.2%).

Chart 5.2. Long-term, youth and female unemployment (% of total).

Source: Eurostat.

On the other hand, long-term unemployment in Poland in 2013 amounted to 42.5%, below the EU average of 47.4%. Moreover, even in 2005, when it was the highest for the entire period from 1997 to 2013, reaching 57.7%, it was not the highest in the EU (3 countries now in the EU had higher rates at that time). It seems that in this respect the situation could have been worse. The reason for this situation is the fact that in the 1990s, when unemployment was reintroduced in Poland, some people being laid off from declining or privatized state-owned companies, especially the elderly persons, were given an opportunity for early retirement or disability pension, which in the long term resulted in an additional burden for the social security system, but also, apparently, reduced (especially the long-term) rate of unemployment.

Chart 5.3. Precarization of labour relations (%).

Source: Eurostat.

As far as the aforementioned precarization of work in Poland is concerned, the most striking circumstance is the explosion of the percentage of temporary employment contracts. While in the last decade of the twentieth century, the percentage of employees with temporary contracts did not exceed 5%, between 2000 and 2005 (a period of record-high unemployment rate), this ratio increased by almost 20 percentage points, from 5.8 % in 2000 to 25.7% in 2005. Since then, it maintains a stable, slightly increasing trend. In 2009 for the first time, Poland overtook Spain, becoming (and remaining to this day) the infamous leader in this respect in the European Union, for which the average percentage of employees with temporary contracts in 2013 was 13.7% (while 26.9% in Poland). The share of self-employed in total employment is also very high. According to the World Bank data, in 2012 it

amounted to 22.4%, which was the fourth highest in the European Union (for which the average for the period was 16.1%). Importantly, the number of self-employed in Poland for at least a decade has been very stable, fluctuating within a range of 2.7-2.9 million people.

Another very important feature of the Polish labour market, indicating an extreme predominance of capital over labour, is a very high average of annual hours actually worked per worker. In 2013, according to the OECD data, it amounted to 1,879 hours, which was the 5th highest result among 30 OECD countries (after Mexico, South Korea, Chile and Russia) and almost 200 hours above average (although the number is steadily declining, this decline is very limited – since 2000, a total of 84 hours). The consequence of this extensive exploitation of labour, combined with precarization of employment, is – among other factors – a small and declining proportion of part-time employees in total employment. In 2013, it amounted to 7.1%, which was the 6th lowest in the European Union, with the average for the 28 countries of 19.6%. Low wage growth relative to productivity growth, high unemployment, as well as more and more precarious employment therefore result in Polish companies, having to choose between an increase in the number of hours worked by hitherto employees, or additional (e.g. part-time) employment, usually decide on the first option. For the same reason, the Polish economy has a permanently low employment rate – below 60% in the years 1997-2012, and only in 2013 reaching 60.0%, while the EU average amounted to 64.1%.

Interestingly, although part-time employment in Poland is very small, involuntary part-time employment is a growing part of it. While in 1997 it was 13.8% of total part-time employment (with the EU15 average of 20.5%), in 2013 it already reached 30.9%, with the EU28 average of 29.3%. Although this percentage is still far from being the highest among the EU countries, its dynamics (124% in 1997-2013 period) may give rise to concern.

Another phenomenon related to the precarization problem is the development of the shadow economy in Poland, particularly in the labour market. According to estimates of the Institute for Market Economics (Krzysztof Łapiński, Marcin Peterlik, Bohdan Wyżnikiewicz, "Szara strefa w polskiej gospodarce", 2014), the size of the shadow economy in Poland amounted to 19.5% of GDP in 2014, representing a slight decrease over the last few years – from 21% in 2010. According to the A.T. Kearney report (Friedrich Schneider, "The Shadow Economy in Europe", 2013), in 2013, this share was higher and reached 24%. However, the most important (although very

limited) is data on the extent of the shadow economy in the labour market; a study carried out by a Polish employers' organization (PKPP Lewiatan) showed that, in 2012, up to 33.2% of Polish companies were employing workers 'in the shadow'.

Chapter 6: Welfare

Poland has a rather limited system of social protection and welfare, which was also almost entirely built in the socialist era. Since the reintroduction of capitalism, it has been limited, disassembled and, whenever possible, privatized. The only exception in this respect is the unemployment benefit, newly introduced under capitalism, which in socialist times of full employment had simply no reason to exist. It is, however, a good example of the attitude of Polish authorities to social policy in the last quarter of a century.

In order to receive an unemployment benefit in Poland, one must demonstrate to have met all three of the following criteria: 1) register in the labour office as unemployed, 2) lack a job offer (including training, vocational training, intervention work or public work) from the labour office, and 3) prove, based on employment history, to have worked for at least 365 days during the 18 months prior registration, which resulted in paying the appropriate amount of social security contribution. The unemployment benefit is paid out for 6 months with the exception of people over 50 years of age, who have worked for at least 20 years: they can use the benefit for a period of one year. In the second half of 2014, basic unemployment benefit in Poland amounted to 831.1 PLN through the first three months of the entitlement and 652.6 PLN for the next months. People with work experience of less than 5 years receive 80% of this amount (664.88 PLN during the first three months, then 522.08 PLN), and those having worked more than 20 years – 120% (997.32 PLN and 783.12 PLN, respectively).

Those funds, in each of the options mentioned above, are however insufficient for one's normal functioning in society. In September 2014, according to the calculations of the Institute of Labour and Social Affairs ("Informacja o wysokości minimum socjalnego we wrześniu 2014 r.", Warsaw, December 12, 2014), the so-called 'social minimum' in Poland ranged from 824.52 PLN for a household of five with three children, to 1058.44 PLN for a single person. Therefore, the unemployment benefit in Poland is most likely not sufficient to cover the social minimum, and only close to achieving this goal in the case of people with long work experience, and only for the first three months of the entitlement. Worse than that, according to the Central Statistical Office, in 2013, only 16.1% of the unemployed in Poland were entitled the benefit, due to the overly restrictive criterion (mentioned in the previous paragraph as criterion no. 3), especially for the long-term unemployed and victims of the

precariousness of the labour market.

Poland also has, introduced in the socialist era, a general state-run health insurance system. It, however, faces many problems in its function, the two most significant of which are chronic underfunding and the progressive decrease in the share of working population entitled to health security. This has most severe consequences for society. As regards the first of these problems, it is well illustrated by OECD data on total expenditures on individual and collective healthcare as a share of GDP: in the years 2000-2012, this ratio for Poland is consistently one of the lowest among OECD countries. In 2000 it was 5.3% (the fourth lowest in the OECD), while in 2012 – 6.3%, the third lowest (after Estonia and Mexico), with the average of 9.0% for the Organisation. In this respect, Poland has also the third worst result in the European Union (after Estonia and Romania). The second problem is associated with advancing of the precarization of labour relations in Poland, mostly in the last fifteen years. Because of it, a growing part of the Polish population has no medical insurance, and therefore cannot use the public health system, ending up stuck with expensive private services. An important social consequence of this is the high percentage of people with unmet needs for medical examination. In 2013, it was 8.8%, which was fifth highest share in the European Union (after Lithuania, Romania, Greece and Bulgaria), with the EU28 average of 3.6%.

There is also a state-run pension scheme in Poland, already briefly discussed above. An addition to it is the so-called nursing supplement, designed to provide additional financial support for needy seniors. This benefit is paid by the Social Security as a supplement to a pension (either disability or retirement one), to support covering costs resulting from the lost or reduced ability to function independently. In March 2015, this benefit amounted to 208.17 PLN per month. The nursing supplement can be granted to a person eligible for disability/retirement pension, if one was deemed completely incapable of work and independent existence (which has to be proven), or when one becomes 75 years of age (then granted automatically).

Education at primary and secondary level in Poland is essentially public and free of charge. Despite the slow development of private education, in 2014 – according to the Central Statistical Office data – as much as 92.8% of primary schools, 88.6% of lower secondary schools and 73.9% of upper secondary schools were public. As part of the education system in the socialist era, there were numerous and varied public vocational secondary schools. This has been, however, strongly limited by the reform of the education system from 1999 on. The government decided then to promote

general education, leading to university studies, allegedly associated with greater flexibility of youth on the labour market. As a result, vocational education has declined. In 1991, 92.5 thousand young people graduated from secondary schools of general education while from vocational schools of all types 351.1 thousand did so; but in 2009, it was already 231.1 thousand in general education and 220.0 thousand in vocational schools. The weight of professional training, especially in jobs that require greater specialization, fell heavily on companies. Since 2012, there have been attempts to rebuild public vocational education, but it will be very difficult to achieve because of the very limited expenditure on education in Poland.

The consequence of limiting vocational and promoting general education, particularly that this coincided with the period of the highest unemployment in Poland, was a massive interest by youth in academic studies. On one hand, studies were supposed to ensure better chances in the labour market. On the other hand, they were a form of 'postponing unemployment' (usually for about five years, since this is how long it takes to obtain master's degree in Poland, as a bachelor's degree was until recently uncommon). This meant a boom in the number of students, not only for free full-time studies in public universities (then available for those who successfully pass entrance exams, now for those who earn the appropriate number of points on matriculation examination). but also on paid evening studies and part-time studies in the same public universities, and – above all – for the emerging and, for at least a decade since then, the rapidly growing sector of private universities. The problem with the latter, however, was a very low quality of teaching, as well as running only low-cost courses of study, not related to the needs of the labour market. Consequently, the boom in higher education did not live up to the hopes of improving the situations of young people. On the other hand, paid studies in private universities blamed that they never reached quantitative advantage over the public university system (in 2013 25.7% of the total of 1.5 million students studied in non-public schools).

Chapter 7: Conclusion

Undoubtedly, the most distinctive feature of Poland's socio-economic order is its political situation (no left in public life or in the media, the neoliberal consensus among virtually all political forces, weakness of the labour unions), leading to a number of permanent pathologies of economic life, particularly in the labour market, and consequently in the distribution of national income. The Polish labour market is characterized by: permanent high unemployment, low part-time employment, long working hours, high job insecurity and extremely low unionization of labour. Along with such features as a high growth of labour productivity combined with a very low labour cost, moderate wage growth, low taxation of capital and its high returns on investment, to a large extent these explain the Polish jobless growth problem. The consequence of the above is that a disproportionate share of the Polish GDP goes to corporations in profits and extremely little falls to employees in the form of wages. As a result, many social problems accrued during twenty-five years of the new Polish capitalism are being petrified, and their solution, without addressing the above-mentioned issues, may occur to be very difficult, if at all possible.

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